

Green Waste Disposal

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ABSTRACT

Green waste includes grass clippings, leaves, tree limbs, Christmas trees, and organic materials. Green waste management practices protect the environment and residents from the detrimental health effects of pollution and climate change. Serious treatment of the environmental issues associated with the dumping of the green wastes is in progress worldwide. This paper provides a short introduction to the green waste disposal.

KEYWORDS: green waste disposal, e-waste, green waste management

INTRODUCTION

Waste generation is an inevitable product of human activities. The waste includes common everyday waste such as food waste (e.g. fruits and vegetables), plastics, papers, polythene, metals, batteries, and textiles. Food waste, consisting of leftover portion of meals and waste from food preparation activities in kitchen and restaurants, is the third largest component of generated waste [1]. Emerging kinds of waste include e-waste, mobile phones, computers, and other kinds of electronic gadget. The major sources of the wastes include households, offices, supermarkets, manufacturer, and other industries. Waste storage and collection form a very crucial stage of waste management. Waste disposal is usually the final step in waste management [2]. Disposal of nuclear fuel and other high-level waste forms is technically challenging. Plastic materials are dangerous to the environment since some chemicals in the material are toxic.

Each country has its own waste disposal system. The government should encourage policies to reduce waste in the industrial sector and manufacturing by reducing tariffs and raising incentives to companies that reduce industrial waste. It is pathetic that some nations, particularly in Africa, still have problems disposing their waste. It was found that during the 1980s nearly 15 African countries were involved in providing dumping sites for hazardous waste (including Ghana, Somalia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Zimbabwe, and South Africa). In return, corrupt officials received money for the provision of the land. The dangers of toxic waste disposal is often overlooked because many do not see it as being important. The African Union has condemned the exporting and shipping unused and unwanted electrical and electronic goods from developed to developing nations [3].

TRADITIONAL WASTE MANAGEMENT

Traditional waste management is regarded as a service, disposing unwanted materials typically to landfill. The waste hierarchy minimizes waste by prevention, minimization, reuse, recycling, and recovery before considering landfill. Circular economy achieves the same result but considers waste as a valuable resource. Transformation of materials through valorization results in a product of added value. Governments are realizing the economic opportunities of valorizing and circulating waste materials, thus eliminating the need for their further disposal [4].

The consumers are expected to dispose product waste and product packaging after the product is consumed. There are three types of waste disposal: residential, commercial, and local government. For example, local government policy typically consists zero waste policy, recycling, and disposal targets.

GREEN WASTE MANAGEMENT

Green waste (garden) includes foliage, leaves, tree limbs, plant residues, fallen flowers, garden refuse, leaf litter, cut grass, weeds and other organic materials discarded from gardens. It contains complex compounds such as cellulose, amino acids, proteins, and carbohydrates. If properly processed, green waste can be a potential resource for energy and other value-added products [5]. Green disposal IT base industries can refurbish and reuse old data centers components, while other unwanted electronics components can be prepared for recycling operations. For effective sustainable waste management, the minimization or reduction of waste at the source is crucial.

Green waste management (SWM) includes access to residential and work site composting, and other opportunities to divert waste from landfills. SWM influences the degree of sustainability of urban environment. It strategically integrates several waste treatment methods to optimize the recovery of recourse and to reduce the volume of wastes. Traditionally, green waste management programs have focused on providing equal service to all residents and to reduce the amount of waste sent to landfills [6].

Green wastes can be managed through either “grasscycling,” or backyard composting.

Grasscycling involves simply leaving grass clippings on the lawn after mowing. This may significantly reduce the volume of grass wastes discarded, save on time spent to rake, and save trash bag. The objective of backyard composting is to allow yard wastes to biologically decompose together to make a stable soil amendment that you can use to return nutrients to your yard. If backyard composting or grasscycling is not feasible, one should join in the recycling effort [7].

CONCLUSION

The production of waste and its disposal using various means is an increasingly undesirable outcome. Green waste is a valuable resource because it contains a high content of oxygen, high moisture content, and alkaline earth metals. Processing of green waste would reduce the quantity of green waste reaching dumping sites or burned. Developing sustainable technologies to utilize green waste is attracting attention [8]. Education on proper disposal of waste is essential to raise awareness.

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